

D5.3 Local and Federated district-level Digital Twins – Month 18

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This deliverable describes the information management and semantic architecture required to support the development of interoperable and scalable Digital Twins for the WILSON project.	

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

AHU	Air Handling Unit
API	Application Programming Interface
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BMS	Building Management System
BOT	Building Topology Ontology
BRICK	Brick Schema (building metadata standard)
CAD	Computer Aided Design
CDE	Common Data Environment
CIMBA	Condition-based Inspection and Maintenance for Building Assets (WILSON predictive maintenance tool)
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DT	Digital Twin
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
EV	Electric Vehicle
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IDS	International Data Spaces
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes (BIM exchange standard)
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
OpenAPI	Open Application Programming Interface (standard for REST APIs)
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PDH	Personalised Data Hub

R2RML	RDB to RDF Mapping Language
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RUL	Remaining Useful Life
SAREF	Smart Appliances REference ontology
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
SOSA/SSN	Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator / Semantic Sensor Network (W3C ontologies for IoT and sensing data)
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TTL	(pronounced 'turtle') stands for "Terse RDF Triple Language"
UC	Use Case
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
USB	Urban Sciences Building (UK pilot site at Newcastle Helix)
WP	Work Package

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The WILSON project develops a semantic Digital Twin (DT) framework, establishing the foundation for the integration, federation, and management of building and district-level data across the project's pilot sites. The work addresses the definition of the information management and semantic architecture required to support the development of interoperable and scalable Digital Twins for the WILSON project.

WILSON introduces a dual-layer semantic framework that underpins both local building Digital Twins and federated district twins. The core alignment layer ensures interoperability through the adoption of shared ontologies (e.g., BOT, SSN/SOSA, SAREF, BRICK), while pilot-specific extensions capture local requirements and unique data structures. This approach balances standardisation and flexibility, allowing WILSON to harmonise heterogeneous datasets across diverse pilots while maintaining data sovereignty and compliance with data space requirements.

The WILSON framework operationalises data integration through Personalised Data Hubs (PDHs). PDH acts as an independent data orchestrator that provides a unified interface for BIM, BMS, IoT and other data retrieval, transformation, and distribution from the pilots, without centralising or providing direct access to the original datasets. It enables data aggregation, semantic harmonisation and alignment using standard ontologies, decentralised data access via distributed query processing and secure data exchange. The federated architecture ensures continuous feedback between physical and digital layers and enabling actionable insights for the various WILSON use cases, including building lifecycle management, predictive maintenance, and energy efficiency.

The minimum WILSON DT model defines a common data vocabulary—comprising *District*, *Building*, *Space*, *System*, *Asset*, *Sensor*, and *Observation* entities—aligned with ISO and W3C standards (BOT 1.1 [1], IFC [2], SAREF [3], Brick Schema 1.3 [4]). This model ensures that all pilot datasets are semantically consistent, traceable, and interoperable. The framework's application is demonstrated in the UK Helix pilot, where the DT data model is proposed by aligning the heterogeneous building datasets from the Urban Sciences Building, The Spark, and The Core buildings.

The WILSON semantic digital twin framework provides an important contribution to WILSON's implementation roadmap by delivering the semantic and technical foundations for interoperable and federated DTs. The framework supports a scalable, standards-based approach to data management that advances the project's objectives for sustainable, data-driven building and district operation. The next phase of the project will focus on extending and validating this framework across all pilot sites, enhancing federation mechanisms, and integration of WILSON energy and non-energy tools with the local and federated WILSON DTs.

2. INTRODUCTION

The information management framework for semantic Digital Twins (DTs) is defined in the WILSON project, with a particular focus on the requirements and core model that will enable the development of both local building DTs and federated district-level DTs.

The WILSON project recognises the increasing complexity of building and district DTs, where information from BIM, IoT devices, BMS, energy networks, and contextual data sources (e.g. weather, occupancy) remains fragmented across formats, vendors, and stakeholders. The project's goal is to overcome this fragmentation through a semantic data mesh architecture that ensures interoperability, scalability, and sovereignty of data.

To achieve this, a semantic framework and federation mechanisms are defined, which underpin the development of building and district-level DTs through:

- definition of semantic building and district DTs in the context of WILSON;
- description of the semantic DT architecture for WILSON;
- specification of core data requirements (structural, operational, quality, interoperability);
- definition of a minimum common data model that enables alignment across pilots.
- pilot-level application of the minimum common data model, focusing on the UK Helix pilot, to demonstrate the framework's implementation.

By focusing on the core model and federation principles, WILSON provides an important foundation for the development of the semantic DTs at building and district levels, their integration with energy and non-energy tools, as well as their implementation across pilots.

2.1. Scope

This document proposes the **information management framework for semantic Digital Twins (DTs)** for WILSON and the development of DTs for WILSON pilot sites, as well as integration with WILSON energy and non-energy tools:

- designing a core data model that can be applied across pilots at consortium level;
- specifying the semantic architecture to enable data integration, interoperability, and federation;
- defining minimum requirements for data quality, completeness, integration and interoperability;
- supporting the development of local and federated DTs through the PDH nodes and following data spaces principles, in line with WILSON "INNI District Digital Twins: federation and data mesh approach"

In addition, an initial analysis of the UK Helix pilot is provided in the context of the proposed framework. Additional pilot-specific details (e.g. data availability, gap analysis, local extensions) will be considered in the next phase of the project, for all WILSON pilot sites.

2.2. Structure

The structure of this document is as follows:

- **Section 3** introduces the WILSON semantic Digital Twin framework, defining core concepts, the layered semantic architecture, and semantic alignment approaches.
- **Section 4** specifies the data requirements, covering structural, operational, data quality, integration and interoperability aspects.
- **Section 5** defines the minimum WILSON DT model, describing the common data vocabulary and schema.
- **Section 6** provide an example of pilot-level application, focusing on the UK Helix pilot, to demonstrate the framework's implementation in practice.
- **Section 7** summarises conclusions and identifies the future work to be carried out during the next phase of the project.

2.3. Relation with other components of the WILSON project

The work carried out in the development of the Semantic and federated Digital Twins at local and district levels is closely related with several other components of the WILSON project (Figure 1):

- **Baseline assessment and performance framework:** The building and district requirements from WILSON pilot sites and the identified use cases provide the context and requirements for defining the semantic data needs of the WILSON DTs. In particular, the predictive maintenance use case (UC4) informs the extensions to the core model and their alignment with the UK pilot datasets.
- **Ontologies for the built environment and energy & non-energy use cases:** The proposed framework builds directly on the ontologies, vocabulary definitions, and semantic strategies. It specifies how these are applied in the development of semantic DTs for pilot sites.
- **Data interoperability for data mesh enabled Digital Twins:** The data requirements and semantic alignment rules are aligned with the PDHs and associated mediation gateways.
- **DT enabled lifecycle data solutions for energy and non-energy uses:** The proposed semantic mappings will enable consistent integration of monitoring and control data, supporting the energy- and non-energy related tools and use cases of WILSON.
- **Integration of technologies and preparation for pilots:** The proposed framework underpins pilot deployment and validation by defining how pilot-specific datasets are semantically aligned and federated. The resulting semantic DT instances are critical for integration testing and interoperability validation within pilot implementation activities.

Figure 1 – Relation of Semantic and federated digital twins at local and district levels with other components of the WILSON project

3. WILSON SEMANTIC DIGITAL TWIN FRAMEWORK

This section presents the core framework guiding the development of semantic federated Digital Twins (DTs) across WILSON pilot sites. It describes the core concepts and context of DTs and semantic mediation, the framework's semantic architecture, use of domain-specific ontologies, and the approach adopted for semantic alignment and knowledge mapping of the DTs.

3.1. Definition and core concepts

The WILSON Semantic Digital Twin Framework builds upon well-established definitions of building and district-level DTs, while extending them with a federated data mesh approach based on semantic data standards.

The WILSON Semantic DT Framework retrieves data from the individual buildings' PDH to construct and continuously update both local (individual building) and federated (district-level) DTs. The semantically enriched information from these DTs is used by the various WILSON services and applications to support decision making and to assess building performance in real time, according to the various WILSON use cases and pilot site requirements.

Digital Twins (DT) are generally understood as digital representations of physical assets, processes, or systems that are continuously updated with real-world data to support monitoring, analysis, and decision-making processes. The concept of Digital is formed of three main parts: a) physical products in real space, b) virtual products in virtual space, and c) the connections of data and information that link the virtual and real products [5]. In the built environment, DTs typically integrate static information models (e.g., CAD, BIM) with dynamic data sources (e.g. BMS, IoT) to provide data-driven platforms that capture as-is geometry and physical properties of buildings and can be used to improve their operational and environmental performance [6,7].

Semantic models have been proposed for Digital Twins implementation to address the heterogeneity of building data by providing machine-interpretable structures that unify BIM, sensor data, geospatial information, and external datasets [7]. This allows DTs to move beyond siloed representations into interoperable knowledge graphs. The Semantic Web Stack [8] provides a layered framework for structured, interoperable data exchange. It progresses from URIs and RDF (for data representation) to RDFS/OWL (for defining vocabularies) and SPARQL/SHACL (for querying and validation). In the WILSON framework, this structure underpins the Vocabulary Hub, Semantic Mediation Gateways, and Knowledge Graphs, ensuring consistent interpretation, validation, and reuse of data across federated Digital Twins. The semantic web stack is therefore a key enabler for WILSON DTs, providing the ability to represent relationships, validate data, and perform reasoning across different information domains to support the various WILSON use cases and pilot site requirements.

Semantic Building (local) Digital Twins are a virtual representation of a building's physical and operational state, enriched with structured, machine-interpretable meaning using

semantic web technologies. In the WILSON project, it integrates static data (e.g. BIM models), dynamic sensor streams (e.g. HVAC, occupancy, CO₂), and operational metadata using standard ontologies such as Building Topology Ontology (BOT) [1], Semantic Sensor Network Ontology (SSN)/ Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator (SOSA) [9], Smart Applications REference ontology (SAREF) [3], and ifcOWL [10]. Building DTs are accessed via the local Personalised Data Hubs (PDHs) – one PDH per building, ensuring controlled data access and enabling real-time monitoring, reasoning, and decision support functions.

Building Digital Twins will be used primarily by the following WILSON innovations: INN1 District Digital Twins: federation and data mesh approach, INN2 Personalised Building Data Hubs (PDHs), INN4 Semantic-aware analytics energy management toolset, INN5 CIMBA: predictive maintenance, INN6 HIBOU: biodiversity and the urban systems, INN7 CONTINIUM: Semantic renovation for material passports, INN9 BIM-enabled Smart Readiness Indicator calculator.

Semantic District Digital Twins are a federated digital representation of a group of buildings, districts, or urban areas that shares semantically aligned data from multiple sources. In WILSON, it aggregates data from distributed building twins (via PDHs), aligns them through shared ontologies, and integrates urban-scale data (e.g. weather, energy grid signals, external sensors) using linked data principles. The district DTs enable cross-building reasoning, benchmarking, and system-level coordination within and across pilots, particularly for use cases of energy flexibility, renovation planning, and other digital services at district scale.

The federation principle ensures that data remains under the control of each participant. Instead of centralising sensitive datasets, a data mesh federation approach is adopted: each PDH acts as a sovereign node that connects securely to raw data sources, and stores and manages its own semantically enriched data, exposing it through standardised connectors/APIs using data spaces. This approach will allow building and district-level DTs to be assembled without compromising sovereignty or privacy.

District Digital Twins will be used primarily by the following WILSON innovations: INN1 District Digital Twins: federation and data mesh approach, INN3 P2P data and services marketplace (blockchain-based), INN6 HIBOU: biodiversity and the urban systems, INN8 Risk and resilience of the built environment.

Semantic Mediation is the process of translating raw or structured data into semantically enriched representations using ontologies and semantic alignment rules. In WILSON, this is achieved through semantic mediation gateways within the PDH architecture, which transform data from heterogeneous formats (e.g., JSON, CSV, MQTT, BIM) into RDF/OWL triples aligned with reference ontologies such as BOT, BRICK, SSN/SOSA, and SAREF. Semantic mediation ensures that data from diverse sources becomes interoperable, queryable, and usable across DT tools and federated services.

Digital Twin maturity levels. Based on the level of integration between different data sources, and the types of data sources in Digital Twins, different DT maturity levels can be considered [6]:

- Level 0: Unstructured/raw data (e.g. point clouds, photogrammetry, drawings – static datasets)
- Level 1: 2D maps or 3D models (e.g. object-based, with no associated metadata – static datasets)
- Level 2: BIM models connected to persistent/static data, and metadata (e.g. documents, drawings, asset management systems)
- Level 3: BIM models enriched with real-time data (e.g. BIM integration with IoT and BMS data)
- Level 4: Two-way data integration and interaction (e.g. Actuation from DT apps/DT UI)
- Level 5: Autonomous operation and maintenance

Table 1 provides an overview of the different DT tools/innovations to be developed in WILSON and their different levels of integration between physical and virtual systems. In the Project, the implementation of DT tools/innovations and their expected level of maturity at the end of the project is pilot and use-case driven. According to the project’s requirements and taking in account the specific pilots’ constraints, the bi-directional data integration and interaction (Level 4) is expected to be achieved only in some of WILSON’s tools and pilots.

Table 1 - WILSON DT innovations maturity level

WILSON DT INN	Maturity level (before WILSON)	Maturity level (after WILSON)	Additional remarks
INN1 – District Digital Twins: Federation & Data Mesh	Level 3	Level 4	Connects multiple building twins and PDHs, enabling bidirectional data flow across districts; Existing tools – Newcastle Urban Observatory – Building and Urban Digital Twins (not integrated)
INN2 – Personalised Building Data Hubs (PDHs)	N/A	Level 3	Integration of BIM, IoT, and operational streams, exposing real-time data via APIs.
INN3 – P2P Data & Services Marketplace	N/A	Level 3/4	Federated interface allowing discovery and use of real-time data; integration with PDHs.
INN4 – Semantic-Aware Analytics	N/A	Level 3	Real-time data/analytical layer in addition to DT data

WILSON DT INN	Maturity level (before WILSON)	Maturity level (after WILSON)	Additional remarks
Energy Management Toolset			
INN5 – CIMBA: Predictive Maintenance	N/A	Level 3/4	Use live sensor data and output of maintenance actions/alerts
INN6 – HIBOU: biodiversity and the urban systems	N/A	Level 3	Integration of dynamic environmental data (weather, soil, etc.) for simulations
INN7 – CONTINIUM Smart Renovation Support Tool	N/A	Level 2	Use of BIM and performance data, but not real-time streams or control
INN8 – Risk and Resilience tool	N/A	Level 3/4	Integration of multiple infrastructures and allows scenario control, consistent with two-way, federated interaction.
INN9 – BIM-enabled Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI)	N/A	Level 2/3	Uses BIM and energy performance data, with optional live input (sensors) to assess smart readiness.

3.2. WILSON DT semantic architecture

This section outlines the semantic architecture that underpins data integration and interoperability across the WILSON tools and pilot sites. The WILSON DT architecture enables the transformation of heterogeneous data streams—originating from BIM models, IoT sensors, legacy BMS systems, and operational platforms—into a semantically enriched and machine-interpretable representation to be used by the various WILSON DT-enabled tools. It ensures that local and federated DTs operate with shared meaning, supporting reasoning, analytics, and standardised data exchanges.

3.2.1. WILSON DT semantic architecture multi-layer model

The proposed semantic architecture follows a multi-layer model inspired by Semantic Web principles and DT reference architectures [11, 12, 13]. Each layer is modular and supports both upstream (data ingestion) and downstream (feedback/control) workflows, i.e. the layers define how data flows from physical infrastructure to WILSON DT-enabled tools, and how feedback from the digital layer (e.g. optimisations, analytics) is incorporated back into the physical buildings/assets.

The proposed layered architecture, summarised in SEQ Table * ARABIC , will provide a shared model across all pilot sites and serves as the foundation for semantic mediation, data integration, and reasoning.

The semantic architecture of WILSON builds upon a layered model and explicitly integrates international standards for Digital Twins and data interoperability. This ensures that the WILSON framework is not only operational within the pilot sites but also reusable and extendable in the context of International Data Spaces and wider DT ecosystems.

Table 2 - WILSON Digital Twin semantic multi-layer architecture – description of layers, key standards and layers' role within WILSON project

Layer / Component	Description & Functions	Key Standards / References	Role in WILSON
Acquisition Layer	Ingests BIM data, IoT streams, historical time series, and other operational datasets from buildings and districts, including metadata (time, source, calibration).	ISO/IEC 30141:2024 - Internet of Things (IoT) – Reference architecture, ISO 12006 (BIM), IFC/ifcOWL	Collects heterogeneous data for pilot twins; ensures metadata quality.
Integration Layer: PDH	Local PDHs act as secure hubs implementing Data Space connectors and access policies. Provide APIs for data access to/from WILSON DT applications.	IDS Reference Architecture	Acts as a data mesh node, enforcing sovereignty and standardised access.
Integration Layer: Vocabulary Hub	Central ontology and vocabulary registry that stores shared concepts, mappings, and equivalence rules used across pilots. Supports ontology versioning, governance, and semantic lookup by mediation gateways and tools.	W3C OWL/RDF, ETSI SAREF, BOT, SSN/SOSA, ISO/IEC 21838 (Ontology Framework)	Provides the authoritative semantic reference for all WILSON components; ensures consistent interpretation of data and alignment across pilots.
Knowledge Layer: Semantic Mediation Gateways	Map raw datasets (BIM, sensors, occupancy, energy) to standard ontologies (BOT, SSN/SOSA, SAREF, BRICK) using transformation pipelines. Aligns heterogeneous sources.	ISO/IEC 21838 (Top-Level Ontologies), W3C R2RML/SHACL	Provide the semantic translation for DT data sources, enabling reasoning

Layer / Component	Description & Functions	Key Standards / References	Role in WILSON
			within and across DTs.
Knowledge Layer: Ontologies & Knowledge Graphs	Dual-layer ontology model: (1) common core for buildings/urban assets; (2) pilot-specific extensions. Supports reasoning, within and across DTs, and federated queries.	BOT, SSN/SOSA, SAREF, BRICK, RealEstateCore, CityGML, GeoSPARQL, etc.	Provides a harmonised, extensible data schema for WILSON DTs.
Representation Layer	Models semantic building DTs and federated district DTs. Captures entities, properties, and behaviours, linking to WILSON simulation and predictive models.	ISO 23247 (Digital Twin Framework), ISO 30146 (Smart City Indicators)	Provides Digital Twin structure for pilots and federated district DTs.
Application Layer: Reasoning & Analytics	Supports the various WILSON services/tools. Federated SPARQL queries, inference, predictive maintenance, energy optimisation. Supports cross-building insights and district-level KPIs.	ISO 23247 (composition & interaction), W3C SPARQL 1.1 Federation	Enables analytics and simulations at local and district scale; implements WILSON KPIs (Task 4.5)
Application Layer: Feedback & Control (Downstream)	Sends optimisation setpoints, maintenance alerts, and energy flexibility commands back to building systems or city-level platforms.	ISO 23247 (Control Aspects), IEC 62541 (OPC UA for Building Automation)	Closes the loop between digital and physical in both building and district twins.
Governance & Security Layer	Policies for data sharing, privacy, and ethics; aligns with GDPR and Data Space usage control (i.e. Trust framework in T5.1). Tracks provenance and consent.	FAIR Principles, IDS Usage Control	Ensures compliance and trust in Digital Twin operations across pilots.

Acquisition Layer:

Data ingestion in WILSON follows the principles of ISO/IEC 30141:2024 - Internet of Things (IoT) – Reference architecture [14] and ISO 12006 for BIM-based information management [15]. This layer captures heterogeneous inputs from BIM models, IoT devices, BMS systems, and historical time series, while preserving essential metadata such as timestamps, sensor calibration, and spatial context. By aligning acquisition with these standards, WILSON ensures consistent data quality and traceability across both building and district DTs, forming the foundation for accurate semantic mapping and analytics.

Integration Layer:

At the integration layer, Personalised Data Hubs (PDHs) implement secure Data Space connectors following the International Data Spaces (IDS) Reference Architecture [11] and Gaia-X Federation Services [16]. This layer ensures data sovereignty and standardised access through policy-based usage control and authentication. PDHs act as the operational nodes of WILSON's federated data mesh, providing APIs for tool access while enforcing local governance. The integration layer also includes the Vocabulary Hub, which serves as a central ontology and vocabulary registry that provides shared concepts, mappings, and equivalence rules across pilots, ensuring alignment and semantic consistency throughout the federation of DTs.

Knowledge Layer:

The knowledge layer manages semantic mediation and ontology alignment between local data and the WILSON Core Model. This process follows ISO/IEC 21838 – Top-Level Ontologies for Interoperability [17], using the W3C RDB to RDF Mapping Language R2RML and SHACL to translate data into structured RDF or JSON-LD formats. The layer comprises two components:

- Semantic Mediation Gateways, which perform schema mapping and transformation from raw BIM, sensor, and energy datasets to standard ontologies such as BOT, SSN/SOSA, SAREF, and BRICK;
- Ontologies and Knowledge Graphs, which apply the dual-layer ontology model (i.e. core plus pilot-specific extensions) to support reasoning and federated queries across WILSON pilots.

Representation Layer:

This layer structures the semantic building and district DTs in accordance with ISO 23247 – Digital Twin Framework for Manufacturing [12] and ISO/IEC 30146 – Smart City ICT Indicators [18]. The representation layer defines how entities, properties, and behaviours are modelled within the WILSON ecosystem, enabling both static and dynamic aspects—structural geometry, operational parameters, behavioural trends, and contextual conditions (e.g. energy flexibility, occupant comfort)—to be represented in an interoperable format. This layer provides the structural and semantic basis for the building-level and federated district-level DTs.

Application Layer:

The application layer enables reasoning, analytics, and integration across WILSON's tools and services. Federated reasoning and distributed analytics aim to support cross-building insights and district-level KPIs. This aligns with ISO 23247's emphasis on the composability and interoperability of DTs, ensuring that WILSON's DTs can seamlessly exchange data and coordinate analyses across building (local) and district-level domains.

Governance Layer:

The WILSON project establishes a comprehensive data governance framework grounded in FAIR data principles, GDPR compliance, and federated data management. These principles ensure that all research and operational data within the project are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) while respecting ethical and legal constraints.

This layer defines policies for privacy, consent, and provenance tracking, ensuring compliance with GDPR and ethical data-sharing practices. It also operationalises WILSON’s innovation INNI – “District Digital Twins: federation and data mesh”, where the PDH acts as the governance enabler within a distributed federation. Data ownership remains with the original providers – primarily the pilot sites – while Personalised Data Hubs (PDHs) act as secure intermediaries for data access based on specific user roles. Through this governance layer, WILSON maintains transparency, accountability, and trust across all pilots and WILSON federated services/applications.

Figure 2 illustrates the data flow diagram underpinning the WILSON Semantic Digital Twin (DT) framework. It represents the full data lifecycle, from acquisition at pilot sites to semantic enrichment, federation, and downstream use in tools and applications.

Figure 2 - WILSON DT Framework data flow diagram

Data Acquisition and PDH Layer

The data acquisition and PDH layer, developed in WPs 7&8, provides the foundation of the architecture, encompassing diverse data sources, including Building Information Models (BIM), Building Management Systems (BMS), IoT sensor streams, and time series datasets collected across pilot sites. These heterogeneous data streams are ingested into the PDH nodes – one per building. Each pilot may have multiple PDH nodes (e.g., PDH Node A, PDH Node B), which expose APIs for data access and sharing for different buildings in the same pilot. The PDH also supports feedback loops to local systems through standardised API/services (e.g., building control and automation subsystems), enabling closed-loop operation and response to optimisation recommendations generated by WILSON tools. The key components in this layer are:

- Semantic Mediation Gateways translate pilot-specific schemas (e.g., IFC, BMS vendor APIs, CSV, or JSON feeds) into a common semantic representation conforming to the WILSON Core Model.
- The Vocabulary Hub serves as the central ontology and vocabulary registry, providing the shared semantic definitions and mapping templates used by the mediation gateways when translating local data into the WILSON Core Model. It ensures consistent interpretation of concepts across pilots and supports versioning and governance of semantic assets.

Semantic Framework and Federation Layer

The semantic layer, developed in WPs 5&6, provides the knowledge representation and interoperability backbone of the WILSON framework. It comprises several key components:

- Each pilot site maintains Semantic Building DTs, which integrate the data from local sources into a structured knowledge graph. These DTs encapsulate both static (BIM-derived) and dynamic (sensor and operational) information.
- A Federated Knowledge Mesh interconnects the individual building twins using common identifiers and shared semantics. This enables data discoverability and interoperability across pilots while maintaining local autonomy.
- The Semantic District Digital Twin aggregates and contextualizes knowledge from multiple buildings and district infrastructures (e.g., energy, mobility, and environmental systems) to support cross-domain analyses and urban-scale reasoning.

Applications and Services Layer

At the top of the architecture, the applications layer includes all WILSON digital tools and services, developed in WPs 9 through 12, that consume or contribute data through the semantic framework. These applications access the federated knowledge graphs through standard interfaces (e.g., SPARQL or GraphQL endpoints, REST APIs) provided by the PDH nodes.

Information exchange occurs between the semantic and application layers where applications query semantically enriched data, perform analyses, and issue control signals or recommendations. These are propagated downstream to the PDH and building control systems, closing the feedback loop between physical and DT.

3.2.2. The role of PDH and Data Spaces within the WILSON semantic DT framework

Within the WILSON semantic DT framework, Personalised Data Hubs (PDHs) and the Data Space Layer play complementary roles in managing and exchanging data.

PDHs act as local integration and harmonisation nodes, ingesting and standardising heterogeneous data sources (e.g., BIM, BMS, IoT, and other data sources) within each pilot. They implement primary data harmonisation, converting local formats into the WILSON Core Model through semantic mediation gateways and exposing APIs for DTs and tool access.

The Data Space Layer enables secondary data sharing and federation across pilots. It applies the International Data Spaces (IDS) Reference Architecture to manage secure, sovereign data exchange between PDHs. Through Data Space connectors and common metadata, semantically harmonised datasets from local PDHs become discoverable and reusable by other sites or WILSON services while maintaining ownership and usage-control policies.

Each PDH node connects to the Data Space through an Data Space Connector, which enforces data usage policies, authentication, and encryption.

Within this framework, semantically enriched metadata from local DTs is published to a Federated Catalogue [11], making datasets discoverable by other WILSON participants under clearly defined access conditions. The use of semantic annotations and standardised metadata profiles—aligned with IDS Information Model and FAIR principles—ensures that shared data assets can be queried, understood, and reused consistently across pilots while preserving ownership and compliance requirements.

Together, these layers establish a two-tier integration structure:

- PDH level: local data curation, harmonisation, and semantic enrichment.
- Data Space level: federated publication, discovery, and controlled sharing between pilots.

This separation ensures scalability and compliance with FAIR principles while supporting both local autonomy and cross-pilot interoperability within the WILSON DT framework.

3.3. Semantic alignment and knowledge representation

The integration of heterogeneous data sources into a DT information management framework represents one of the central challenges in developing semantic DTs within WILSON. Each pilot site contributes a variety of datasets, ranging from BIM models and sensor data to contextual and behavioural information, which must be harmonised to be

adopted across pilots, and enable the development of district-level DTs. To address this challenge, WILSON adopts a strategy based on semantic alignment and structured knowledge representation.

Semantic alignment in this context refers to the process of ensuring that concepts, attributes, and relationships from different data sources are expressed in a consistent and interoperable manner. This is necessary to overcome the fragmentation inherent in building, energy, maintenance, and other data sources, where different pilots may rely on separate conventions, terminologies, or data exchange formats.

WILSON follows a **dual-layer approach**: a **core alignment layer** ensures interoperability across pilots by relying on widely accepted standards, while **pilot-specific extensions** allow for the incorporation of unique datasets or local requirements. These extensions are linked back to the core layer through defined alignment rules, ensuring that they remain interoperable and discoverable at the federation level. This strategy is based on the principles of modularity and interoperability defined in ISO/IEC 21838 - Top-Level Ontologies [17], where domain-specific models are harmonised under a shared structural framework. Figure 3 provides an overview of the WILSON knowledge representation strategy according to the dual-layer semantic alignment approach.

Figure 3 - WILSON knowledge representation strategy - dual-layer semantic alignment approach

The knowledge representation strategy provides the foundation for this semantic alignment. Raw data such as time series of energy consumption, indoor environmental measurements, or occupancy data are enriched with contextual meaning. For example, a numerical temperature value is not merely treated as a sensor reading but is linked to its associated space, equipment, and operational context, enabling its use in broader analyses such as identifying overheating risks or assessing energy efficiency. Representation in this enriched manner supports rule-based reasoning, in which logical conditions and dependencies can be applied across datasets. For instance, an automated reasoning process might infer that if CO₂ levels exceed a defined threshold while occupancy remains high, then additional ventilation measures should be activated. The code snippet below in TTL syntax illustrates this example using existing ontologies:

```

@prefix sosa: <http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/> .
@prefix saref: <https://saref.etsi.org/core/> .
@prefix brick: <https://brickschema.org/schema/1.1/Brick#> .
@prefix schema: <https://schema.org/> .
@prefix event: <http://purl.org/NET/c4dm/event.owl#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
@prefix : <https://wilson-project.eu/helix/> .

:Room101 a brick:Room .
:CO2Sensor123 a sosa:Sensor ;
    sosa:observes saref:CO2Concentration .
  
```

```

:HighCO2Observation a sosa:Observation ;
  sosa:hasResult :HighCO2Level ;
  sosa:madeBySensor :CO2Sensor123 ;
  sosa:resultTime "2025-10-15T10:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime .

:Alert001 a saref:Alert ;
  saref:relatesToAsset :VentUnit45 ;
  schema:actionStatus schema:PotentialActionStatus .

:VentUnit45 a brick:Fan ;
  schema:serviceStatus schema:Active .

:Service001 a schema:Service ;
  schema:serviceType "Predictive Maintenance" ;
  schema:provider :HelixFMCompany ;
  schema:areaServed :Room101 .
    
```

This enriched representation also enables advanced query and analysis mechanisms. Rather than operating on isolated datasets, WILSON supports semantic queries that can traverse building structures, systems, assets, and sensor data to provide integrated insights. Such capabilities are consistent with the objectives of ISO 23247 – Digital Twin Framework for Manufacturing [12], which, while focusing on manufacturing, establishes transferable principles for structuring DTs across domains through consistent data representation and composability.

A further dimension of WILSON’s framework is its capacity for linking and federation. At the building level, semantic alignment ensures internal consistency within each pilot’s Personalised Building Data Hub (PDH). At the district level, however, a federated approach is required to enable cross-building and cross-pilot integration without centralising sensitive datasets. The semantic alignment strategy extends beyond individual pilot ontologies to support federated knowledge exchange across the WILSON ecosystem. Each pilot’s semantic building or district twin is implemented as a local knowledge graph—governed by its PDH—which conforms to the shared WILSON Core Model while maintaining site-specific extensions. These local graphs interconnect through a Federated Knowledge Mesh, enabling distributed reasoning and cross-site querying without centralising raw data.

Federation is achieved by adopting common identifiers, shared entity templates, and metadata profiles sourced from the Vocabulary Hub (see *Deliverable 5.2*). This ensures that concepts retain semantic equivalence across pilots, allowing district-level or cross-pilot analytics to operate seamlessly.

Following the data mesh architecture, each PDH acts as a semantically aligned but autonomous node—responsible for its own data quality, access policies, and updates—while contributing to a coherent federated view.

At the district level, federated reasoning combines data from multiple building DTs to represent e.g. energy, and environmental systems as interconnected subsystems. This supports higher-order use case requirements such as energy load balancing, and predictive maintenance across buildings. The approach aligns with ISO 23247-1 – Digital

Twin Framework [12] and with the emerging European frameworks for data sharing, particularly the International Data Spaces (IDS) and Gaia-X initiatives, which promote federated architectures that guarantee interoperability while preserving sovereignty and GDPR compliance [11, 16].

In practice, WILSON's semantic alignment and knowledge representation strategy will enable pilots to exchange and compare information without the need for bespoke mappings at every interface. It ensures that data quality and integrity can be validated systematically, for example through schema and rule validation. Most importantly, it provides a scalable pathway from building-level DTs to district-scale urban DTs, where insights can be aggregated across sites for planning, benchmarking, and optimisation. By embedding meaning, structure, and interoperability directly into the data layer, WILSON ensures that its semantic DT framework is not only technically robust but also aligned with standards and governance frameworks.

4. DATA REQUIREMENTS SPECIFICATION

This section specifies the core data requirements for the WILSON semantic DT framework. The purpose of these requirements is to provide a minimum common structure that all pilot sites must support, ensuring semantic interoperability and enabling federation into district-scale DTs. While pilot- and tool-specific extensions are addressed in other deliverables, this section defines the baseline that guarantees comparability, consistency, and scalability across the project.

4.1. Structural requirements

The structural requirements define the static structure of the core data model, ensuring that all pilots describe buildings, systems, and assets in a consistent manner. Structural information requirements enable DTs to be linked to their physical buildings/assets and provides the foundation upon which operational data can be linked.

At minimum, every local PDH and associated DT should represent:

- **Building:** a uniquely identifiable object with mandatory attributes *BuildingID*, *Name*, additional non-mandatory attributes including address, year of construction, and typology. Geometric and topological data should be included to support visualisation and spatial reasoning.
- **Space:** subdivisions of buildings (e.g. floors, rooms, functional zones) with containment relationships. Each space must have attributes such as *SpaceID*, *Type*, and geometric descriptors (area, volume).
- **System:** representations of technical systems such as HVAC, electrical networks, renewable generation, or storage. Attributes must capture system type, capacity, and operational characteristics.
- **Asset/Component:** the physical equipment composing systems (e.g. boilers, heat pumps, PV inverters, valves). Each asset requires identifiers, manufacturer/model information, installation date, and operational status.
- **Sensor/Actuator:** logical or physical devices capturing measurements or performing control actions. They must include unique identifiers, measurement/control type, and associated units.
- **Observation/Measurement:** time-stamped values generated by sensors or actuators, linked to specific assets, systems, or spaces.

Relationships such as *Building contains Space*, *System composedOf Asset*, or *Asset measuredBy Sensor* are needed for structural consistency. These requirements are aligned with ISO 12006-3:2022 - Framework for object-oriented building information [15] and ISO 23386:2020 - Building information modelling and other digital processes used in

construction – Methodology to describe, author and maintain properties in interconnected data dictionaries [19], ensuring compatibility with BIM-based data sources.

4.2. Operational data requirements

In addition to static data requirements, DTs require dynamic operational data to remain synchronised with the physical environment and support predictive or prescriptive services. This data is typically in time series format and event driven.

At minimum, the WILSON core model requires the following operational data:

- **Time series environmental conditions:** temperature, humidity, CO₂, lighting, and air quality metrics.
- **System operation metrics:** energy consumption, generation, storage levels, and equipment setpoints.
- **Occupancy data:** presence or count data (measured via sensors or schedules), which enables load profiling and comfort modelling.

Each operational dataset must be accompanied by metadata on time (timestamp, frequency, time zone), measurement unit, and data source. These requirements are consistent with ISO/IEC 30141:2024 – Internet of Things (IoT) – Reference architecture [14] and IEC 61968 – Application integration for system operations [20], ensuring reliable system interoperability.

4.3. Data quality

For semantic DTs to support advanced analytics and cross-pilot benchmarking, data quality must be systematically assured. The following dimensions and corresponding WILSON quantitative KPIs (defined in *Deliverable D4.5*) define the thresholds for completeness, accuracy, consistency, and traceability of WILSON DTs. Thresholds are defined as progressive targets based on ISO 8000-61 data quality management practices [21], they are not absolute compliance levels:

- **Completeness:** measures the extent to which mandatory and optional data fields are populated for each pilot and whether key entities (buildings, spaces, systems, assets, sensors) are represented in the semantic DTs. These KPIs ensure that the datasets integrated into the DTs are sufficiently populated to enable valid analytics and simulations according to WILSON use cases.
 - **Relevant KPIs:**
 - **KPI 3 – Data Completeness (Mandatory Data):** Percentage of mandatory data fields filled for each building/district dataset.
 - **KPI 4 – Data Completeness (Optional Data):** Percentage of optional fields populated beyond mandatory requirements.

- **KPI 3:** $\geq 80\%$ of mandatory metadata fields populated.
- **KPI 5:** $\geq 75\%$ of datasets based on site-specific data.
- **KPI 8:** 100% of operational PDHs with active provenance logging (with log completeness improving over time).

4.4. Integration and interoperability requirements

The WILSON framework is built around the principle of a federated data mesh, where each PDH node maintains local sovereignty but aligns with a shared semantic structure. For this approach to work, specific integration and interoperability requirements must be met:

- **Standard APIs:** each pilot must expose its core data model via APIs (REST, GraphQL, or Data Space connectors), ensuring access to structural and operational data.
- **Semantic mediation:** raw data arriving in non-semantic formats (CSV, JSON, BMS exports) must be mapped into the WILSON core model before federation. This ensures that heterogeneous sources are harmonised at the semantic layer.
- **Federated queries:** PDHs must enable distributed query capabilities (e.g. SPARQL federation or graph-based APIs) so that district-level queries can be executed without centralising data.
- **Compliance with FAIR principles:** all core datasets must be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, ensuring compatibility with European data spaces (e.g. those developed under Gaia-X and International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) frameworks).

By enforcing these integration requirements, WILSON ensures that local DTs remain interoperable at the district level while respecting sovereignty and GDPR obligations.

5. MINIMUM WILSON DIGITAL TWIN MODEL

To ensure interoperability across pilots while retaining flexibility for local requirements, WILSON defines a dual-level data modelling strategy. This is implemented using a core model (common to all pilots) and extension models (specific to local datasets and use cases). The models are expressed in a standard UML-based notation, enabling clear definition of entities, attributes, and relationships agnostic to specific ontologies. Federation is achieved by allowing each PDH node to implement the core model and add its own extensions.

The **Minimum WILSON DT model** is designed to represent the smallest common set of classes, attributes, and relationships required to implement building and district twins across all pilot sites. It provides a baseline for semantic interoperability, ensuring that federated queries and cross-site benchmarking can be executed even where local extensions differ. In the federated architecture, this schema functions as the core layer of every local PDH knowledge graph, while pilot-specific extensions capture specific use case requirements (e.g., district-energy networks, biodiversity requirements, investment requirements, predictive maintenance, etc).

The minimum model includes the following entities:

- **District:** with core identifiers and attributes.
- **Building:** with core identifiers and attributes.
- **Space:** with containment relationships.
- **System:** with type and capacity descriptors.
- **Asset/Component:** linked to systems.
- **Sensor/Actuator:** linked to assets or spaces.
- **Observation:** time-stamped values linked to sensors.

Each local implementation instantiates these core entities while linking them through persistent identifiers and provenance metadata compatible with the Federated Catalogue defined in the Data Space layer. This ensures that datasets and services can be advertised, discovered, and reused across the WILSON network under controlled conditions.

Extensions for specific pilots are implemented as UML specialisations but are always mapped back to these core entities. Federation relies on the core model to ensure comparability. The resulting structure enables district-level aggregation and cross-domain reasoning, forming the basis for the Semantic District DTs. In this configuration, the minimum model operates both as a unifying and scalable semantic standard for federated data exchange, consistent with the principles of the IDS Reference Architecture and FAIR data management.

The UML Class Diagram in Figure 4 presents the generic district-level core model that underpins the WILSON semantic DT framework. This model is intentionally pilot-independent, defining only the minimal classes and relationships that are common across all demonstration sites.

Figure 4 - WILSON core Digital Twin data model

At its centre is the *District* class, which aggregates multiple *Buildings*. Each *Building* is composed of *Spaces* and *Systems*, which in turn contain *Assets*. *Assets* are monitored by *Sensors*, and these generate *Observations*. This hierarchical structure provides a simple but robust structure capable of representing the essential aspects of any building or district.

This minimal model is aligned with international standards for construction and DTs. Table 3 provides the alignment between WILSON Core model entities and reference standards/ontologies. By grounding the WILSON core model in these standards, the framework ensures interoperability not only across pilots, but also with wider European and international initiatives such as Gaia-X and the International Data Spaces (IDS) Association.

Table 3 – Alignment between WILSON DT core model entities and reference standards/ontologies

WILSON Core Entity	Reference Class / Standard Alignment	Description	Key Standard(s)
District	CityObjectGroup	Represents an aggregation of multiple buildings and infrastructures (e.g. energy, mobility, environment) forming a district-level twin.	ISO 19157-1:2023 [22]
Building	bot:Building / IfcBuilding	Represents an individual physical building and its associated metadata such as ownership, use, and geolocation.	BOT [1], IFC [2]
Space	bot:Space / IfcSpace	A physical or functional zone within a building (e.g. room, corridor, floor zone). Used to link spatial context with sensors and assets.	BOT [1], IFC [2]
System	saref:DeviceGroup / brick:System / IfcSystem	Represents technical systems such as HVAC, lighting, or electrical distribution that connect assets and sensors.	SAREF [3]; Brick Schema 1.3 [4], IFC [2]
Asset / Component	saref:Device / brick:Equipment / IfcAsset	Represents components within a system (e.g. pump, fan, EV charger). Provide the link between physical equipment and their monitoring points.	SAREF [3]; Brick Schema 1.3 [4], IFC [2]
Sensor / Actuator	sosa:Sensor / sosa:Actuator / IfcSensor / IfcActuator	Devices that capture observations or perform control actions on assets and systems.	W3C SSN / SOSA Ontology [9]
Observation	sosa:Observation	A single measurement or data record generated by a sensor or actuator, including timestamp, unit, and value.	W3C SSN / SOSA Ontology [9], IFC [2]

Pilot-specific extensions are mapped back to this core model, ensuring that additional classes do not compromise interoperability. This approach allows each pilot to meet its own requirements while maintaining compatibility with the federated district twin and ensures that benchmarking and cross-pilot analytics can be executed across the various WILSON district pilot sites. Each pilot requires additional concepts or attributes depending on its use cases. These are modelled as extensions of the core classes, using standard UML mechanisms such as specialisation (inheritance) and association extensions.

6. IMPLEMENTATION – UK PILOT SITE

6.1. Site overview

The UK pilot site for WILSON is in the Newcastle Helix innovation district, a mixed-use urban campus developed through a partnership between Newcastle University, Newcastle City Council and private stakeholders (Figure 5). Within the current project scope, the pilot focuses on three representative buildings at Helix: Urban Sciences Building (USB), The Spark, and The Core. These three buildings provide a diversity of typologies and system maturities (higher education research facility, collaborative workspace, and commercial office respectively), which makes Helix an appropriate demonstrator for testing the WILSON semantic DT framework across heterogeneous operational contexts. The Urban Sciences Building is a flagship living laboratory and is reported to host over a thousand embedded sensors and advanced BMS/CDE infrastructure. In contrast, The Spark and The Core’s energy supply is provided by the Helix District Energy Centre, and these two buildings include a lower amount of real-time instrumentation, providing heterogeneity to validate the proposed semantic mediation and federation approach in WILSON.

Helix also benefits from campus-level shared infrastructure (district heating, sitewide EV charging points) which allows use cases to consider both single-building DTs, as well as a federated district twin that encompass shared services and cross-building interactions. The mixed ownership/management model of the site (several building managers/stakeholders) is an important operational constraint that must be considered in governance, access control and PDH and data spaces implementation. As a consequence, the UK pilot site was allocated as the frontrunner for the UC1 “Decentralised multi-source data management”, and UC4 “Predictive maintenance”, which will be demonstrated through the implementation of the CIMBA predictive maintenance tool (described in *Deliverable D11.1*). Additional information about the UK pilot site can be found in *Deliverable D4.1*.

Figure 5 - The UK pilot (Newcastle HELIX)

6.2. Data availability and gap analysis

The results from a structured survey carried out in Task 4.1 (Deliverable D4.1), together with the mobilisation documentation collected during the current reporting period, show that Helix already provides a substantial amount of structured building information and operational data, but that the availability and granularity vary significantly between buildings. The key observations are:

- **Urban Sciences Building (USB)** – USB is the most instrumented facility in the pilot, with extensive sensor deployments (environmental sensors, sub-metering, occupancy and specialised IoT feeds). It uses a centralised BMS and stores data in a mix of local and cloud systems. USB provides data in time series format through the REST API which can be used for real-time analytics. USB’s BIM data can be leveraged for semantic alignment.
- **The Spark** – The Spark is connected to the Helix District Energy Centre (district heating) and is supported by a comprehensive “Mobilisation Master Pack” – including an asset register. This documentation provides rich static information (asset make/model/location, condition scores and lifecycle reports), which is especially valuable for predictive maintenance model development. However, dynamic (high-frequency) operational streams are limited, and where available they are often provided as aggregated reports rather than native time series data.
- **The Core** – The Core is the least instrumented of the three buildings for the purposes of WILSON: monitoring tends to be coarser (aggregated utility reports and periodic meter readings), and its management systems are more decentralised. The Core is still useful as a test case for how the WILSON framework integrates lower-resolution data sources into semantic DTs.

Considering the currently available data sources for the Helix UK pilot, the main data gaps and constraints relevant to the WILSON core model and use cases are:

1. **Heterogeneous temporal granularity.** Some sources provide high-frequency time series (USB), while others only monthly/aggregated billing or periodic reports (Core, Spark). This limits uniform application of real-time analytics unless a data normalisation approach is implemented.
2. **Distributed storage & access.** Data is stored in a mixture of on-premises and cloud systems (USB, university servers), and access mechanisms differ per building; credential management and connector standardisation are required before full integration.
3. **Maintenance and historical logs accessibility.** Maintenance records and work-order historical data exist (notably for The Spark) but are not yet consistently structured or easily queryable across buildings; this is a critical limitation for predictive maintenance model training and KPI validation.

4. **Provenance and licensing constraints.** Some data streams (e.g., research/observatory feeds) require ethical approvals or have restricted licences; provider metadata and licence terms must be captured and enforced in the PDH layer to ensure compliant sharing. The USB API example already demonstrates how provider/contact/licence metadata can be associated with time series entries and must be preserved. This approach can be adopted for the other Helix buildings as well as other pilots in WILSON.

To operate reliably across Helix, the Helix DT model must (a) accommodate mixed temporal resolutions (support for native time series and aggregated metrics), (b) require standard provenance metadata for every dataset, and (c) define a minimal set of static attributes (asset registers, location, manufacturer/model, installation date, condition) that must be provided to enable cross-pilot benchmarking and predictive models. These align with the envisaged minimum model of WILSON (*District, Building, Space, System, Asset, Sensor, Observation*) and with the CIMBA (Predictive maintenance tool) requirements for asset metadata and historical maintenance records.

6.3. Knowledge model application

WILSON's **dual-layer approach** will be applied to the UK pilot at Newcastle Helix for the development of the knowledge (semantic) layer of the pilot, consisting of:

1. A **core alignment layer**, providing the shared vocabulary and minimal schema common to all pilots.
2. **Pilot-specific extensions**, representing Helix-specific concepts such as district heating nodes, site-wide EV infrastructure, and Urban Observatory sensor feeds.

This strategy ensures that data from the Helix buildings (Urban Sciences Building, The Spark, and The Core) can be represented in a consistent way while capturing the particularities of the local datasets.

At the **building level**, the semantic structure follows the WILSON core model with the addition of extensions from the USB OpenAPI specification. Each building is defined through the core classes *Building, Space, System, Asset, Sensor, and Observation*, which provide the minimal semantic structure. Extensions such as *Entity, Feed, Timeseries, and TimeseriesEntry* are used to capture the way IoT data streams are structured in practice. *Entities* represent physical or logical sub-spaces (e.g. a room or floor), *Feeds* capture logical sensor channels, *Timeseries* represent continuous data streams, and *TimeseriesEntries* correspond to individual observations. These extensions map directly onto the WILSON core concepts, ensuring semantic alignment and consistency.

At the **district level**, the Helix pilot demonstrates how multiple building twins are federated into a single district DT. The *District* entity aggregates the three Helix buildings and integrates shared infrastructure such as the District Energy Centre and EV charging points. Pilot-specific extensions are used to represent these infrastructures explicitly, for example: *DistrictHeatingNode* for energy network components, *EVChargerPoint* for charging stations,

and *UrbanObservatoryFeed* for data streams provided by Newcastle's Urban Observatory. This federated representation will support cross-building analytics, energy optimisation, and predictive maintenance use cases.

The mapping of Helix datasets to the WILSON model will follow these rules:

- **BIM data** mapped to **Building / Space / Asset**. BIM models provided for USB, The Spark, and The Core will be mapped to the WILSON *Building* and *Space* classes. Asset registers (e.g. for AHUs, pumps, EV chargers) will populate *Asset* entities with manufacturer and model metadata. The code snippet below in TTL syntax illustrates this example using existing ontologies:

```
@prefix : <https://wilson-project.eu/helix/> .
@prefix bot: <https://w3id.org/bot#> .
@prefix schema: <https://schema.org/> .

:USB_Building a bot:Building ;
  schema:name "Urban Sciences Building" ;
  bot:hasSpace :Some_USB_Lab ;
  bot:hasElement :USB_AHU_x .

:USB_Lab_2F a bot:Space ;
  schema:name "Second Floor Lab" .

:USB_AHU_01 a schema:Product ;
  schema:manufacturer "Some Manufacturer" ;
  schema:model "Some model" .
```

- **BMS / IoT feeds** mapped to **Sensor / Observation (Timeseries)**. Real-time building management system (BMS) feeds, available at the USB and selected systems in other buildings, will populate the *Sensor* and *Observation* entities. Where structured APIs are available (as in the USB OpenAPI), the *Entity-Feed-Timeseries* chain will be preserved to maintain semantic richness. Aggregated datasets (e.g. hourly averages) will also be represented as *Observations*, with metadata describing aggregation level and sampling frequency. Provenance and licence metadata from data providers will be preserved, supporting FAIR data principles. The code snippet below in TTL syntax illustrates this example using existing ontologies:

```
@prefix : <https://wilson-project.eu/helix/> .
@prefix sosa: <http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .

:USB_TempSensor_2F a sosa:Sensor ;
  sosa:observes :AirTemperature ;
  sosa:madeObservation :Obs_2025_10_24_1200 .

:Obs_2025_10_24_1200 a sosa:Observation ;
  sosa:hasResult "21.3"^^xsd:float ;
  sosa:resultTime "2025-10-24T12:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime .
```

- **Asset registers & maintenance logs** mapped to **Asset / MaintenanceEvent**. The Spark's mobilisation pack includes structured condition scores and lifecycle estimates. These will be mapped to attributes of the *Asset* class (e.g. *conditionScore*,

remainingLifetime). Maintenance actions will be captured as *MaintenanceEvent*, linked to *ExtendedAsset* metadata. This integration underpins CIMBA's predictive maintenance tool, which requires asset health and remaining useful life (RUL) indicators. The code snippet below in TTL syntax illustrates this example using existing ontologies:

```
@prefix : <https://wilson-project.eu/helix/> .
@prefix schema: <https://schema.org/> .

:Spark_Pump_03 a schema:Product ;
  schema:name "Heating Pump x" ;
  schema:manufacturer "Manufacturer Name" ;
  schema:model "Heating Pump model" ;
  schema:additionalProperty [
    schema:name "conditionScore" ;
    schema:value "0.80"
  ] .

:Spark_Pump_03_Maint_2025_05_14 a schema:MaintenanceEvent ;
  schema:object :Spark_Pump_x ;
  schema:startDate "2025-01-01" ;
  schema:description "Bearing replacement" .
```

At the implementation level, semantic mediation gateways will be deployed in the Personalised Data Hubs (PDH). These gateways translate heterogeneous data formats (e.g. IFC BIM exports, BMS vendor APIs, CSV files) into the WILSON semantic model. For Helix, the gateways will also handle pilot-specific extensions (*DistrictHeatingNode*, *EVChargerPoint*, *UrbanObservatoryFeed*), ensuring that they remain interoperable with the core model through explicit alignment rules.

Finally, the knowledge layer will include quality metadata metrics such as completeness, accuracy, and traceability, derived from the WILSON data quality KPIs as described in Section 4.3. These indicators ensure that datasets meet minimum thresholds for completeness (KPI 3–4: $\geq 80\%$ for mandatory and $\geq 60\%$ for optional fields), accuracy (KPI 5 and KPI 7.1: $\geq 75\%$ of verified data sources and API response times ≤ 2 s for 90 % of queries), and traceability (KPI 3, 5, 8: $\geq 80\%$ of mandatory metadata fields populated and 100 % of operational PDHs maintaining provenance logs). This enables WILSON tools to select the most appropriate data for their use cases – for example, CIMBA (Predictive Maintenance tool) can use high-quality, high-frequency time series to train predictive maintenance models, while other tools may rely on lower-resolution aggregated datasets for benchmarking and performance assessment.

Figure 6 provides the UML diagram for the WILSON DT data model for Helix UK pilot, highlighting the implementation of the proposed dual-layer modelling approach. The core model entities are represented in white, while pilot-specific extensions, representing Helix-specific concepts are highlighted in orange, represented as extensions (or inherited by) the core model.

Figure 6 - WILSON Digital Twin data model for Helix UK pilot

6.4. PDH deployment strategy

Personalised Data Hubs (PDHs) described in *Deliverable 7.1* act as the integration and control points for the Helix pilot, forming the link between local data sources, the semantic DT layer, and the wider WILSON Data Space. For the UK pilot, the PDH deployment strategy must support the following functions:

- Connectors to heterogeneous sources.** The PDH implements connectors to ingest data from BIM exports (IFC), BMS endpoints (e.g., DesigoCC or SystemsLink), IoT APIs (i.e. USB OpenAPI), and static data. Each connector translates incoming payloads into the PDH's internal model while preserving provenance, licensing, and update

metadata. These connectors enable consistent ingestion of both semantic and non-semantic data streams, establishing the foundation for harmonised DT operations.

- Semantic mediation gateways.** Each PDH hosts a mediation layer that maps local data to the WILSON Core Model and publishes semantically enriched views (RDF/JSON-LD or aligned REST resources). Mediation gateways perform three key functions: (1) convert non-semantic data streams into structured semantic representations; (2) attach provenance, licence, and quality metadata; and (3) expose discovery metadata so that federated queries can be executed without centralising raw data. This mechanism ensures interoperability and data sovereignty across multiple building owners within the Helix site. The mediation layer interacts with the Vocabulary Hub (as defined in *Deliverable 5.2*) to ensure consistent terminology, alignment with shared ontologies, and long-term schema governance.
- Support for tool integration (CIMBA and others).** The PDH provides standardised APIs for WILSON tools and services. For CIMBA, the PDH must supply access to asset registries, maintenance histories, high-frequency time series for critical equipment, and contextual external data such as weather and occupancy. Where data gaps exist (e.g. limited sampling in the Core or Spark buildings), the PDH could expose metadata describing these gaps to support adaptive model strategies such as transfer learning or synthetic data augmentation (as described in *Deliverable 11.1*).

At the implementation level, the PDH follows a containerised, service-oriented architecture, enabling modular deployment, secure API exposure, and scalability across pilot environments. It hosts the local semantic knowledge graphs that underpin the Helix Building and District DTs, facilitating bidirectional data exchange between the physical and digital assets, and WILSON tools and services.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The WILSON semantic Digital Twin framework underpins the development of building and district DTs in the WILSON project. The proposed framework defines how heterogeneous building and district data can be semantically aligned, federated, and applied in support of the project's objectives for sustainable and data-driven building and district DTs development.

The central outcome is the definition of a **dual-layer knowledge model** consisting of a **core alignment layer**, based on widely accepted standards and reference ontologies, and **pilot-specific extensions**, designed to capture the specific data requirements and infrastructures of WILSON pilot sites. The core model – comprising classes for *District, Building, Space, System, Asset, Sensor, and Observation* – ensures semantic consistency and interoperability across pilots. Pilot-specific extensions, such as *Entity-Feed-Timeseries* chains in the UK pilot, provide the flexibility to represent local data sources without fragmenting the overall framework. This dual-layer approach offers both robustness and adaptability and aligns with best practices established in various standards.

The framework also formalises the role of semantic mediation gateways, which operate at the interface between raw data sources and the semantic layer. These gateways translate heterogeneous formats – including BIM IFC exports, BMS vendor APIs, IoT time series, and asset registers – into the WILSON semantic model, enabling integration within the Personalised Data Hubs (PDHs). By embedding metadata for provenance, licensing, and quality, the gateways ensure that data consumers such as WILSON tools can access datasets that are suitable for their applications.

The Newcastle Helix pilot has provided the first example implementation of the framework. Building-level data requirements for the Urban Sciences Building, The Spark, and The Core were aligned with the core semantic layer and extended with pilot-specific classes. These alignments demonstrate how diverse datasets – including BIM models, IoT sensor streams, and asset registers – can be semantically harmonised to support specific cases, in particular for predictive maintenance. At the district level, the aggregation of these buildings into a federated model illustrates the potential of the WILSON framework to scale beyond individual buildings and support district-level use cases.

In addition to the UK pilot, the developed conceptual structure has been designed with federation in mind. By ensuring that all pilots map back to a minimal shared vocabulary, the framework creates the foundation for cross-site interoperability. This is a crucial enabler for benchmarking, comparative analysis, and the scalability of DT applications beyond the building-level and towards district-level twins.

In summary, the developed semantic DT framework seeks to address the key challenges of heterogeneity, interoperability, and scalability in the WILSON project. By providing a standardised yet flexible foundation for integrating building and district data, it lays the groundwork for the implementation of the various energy and non-energy based WILSON tools, the operation of federated PDHs, and the project goal of supporting the various WILSON use cases at the pilot sites.

7.1. Implications for future work

The following areas will be prioritised in the continuation of this work during the next phase of the WILSON project:

- Federation detailing:** The federation aspect of the WILSON framework will be refined further. This includes strengthening query federation across PDHs, ensuring secure and scalable integration with IDS/Gaia-X compliant data spaces, and formalising governance models that guarantee data sovereignty, privacy, and compliance.
- Application to remaining pilot sites:** While the UK pilot has provided a first proof of concept, the framework will now be extended and validated across the other WILSON pilots in Spain, Italy, and Switzerland. Each pilot will test the adaptability of the core model to diverse data contexts, infrastructures, and use cases.
- Update and expansion at the UK pilot site:** The Newcastle Helix implementation will be updated to address current data gaps, expand coverage to additional datasets within the identified buildings, and improve real-time data integration.
- Integration with WILSON tools:** Ongoing work will link the semantic twins with WILSON tools/services (i.e. predictive maintenance (CIMBA), energy flexibility tools, biodiversity monitoring, and risk/resilience applications, etc.), ensuring that the federation model supports both energy and non-energy innovations.
- Cross-pilot harmonisation and scalability:** Upcoming work will explore how the semantic DT framework can be implemented across different domains, and how federation principles can be scaled beyond the WILSON pilots to inform future DT ecosystems.

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